

POSSIBILITIES TO MANAGE AND ELIMINATE THE STRESS OF MANAGERS ON THE BASIS OF INNOVATIVE MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. Innovative activity characteristic of modern conditions, one level or any production enterprise. Even if the company is not the leader in the innovative market, sooner or later it will be faced with the need to replace morally obsolete technologies and products. This article analyzes issues such as psychological assessment of employees' mental state and determination of ways to eliminate them through management psychology, and also provides information about the goals and tasks of management psychology.

Keywords: innovation, management, psychology, employee, employer, management, enterprise, system, brand, business, management, interface, market, operational, marketing.

ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ И УСТРАНЕНИЯ СТРЕССА МЕНЕДЖЕРОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ

Аннотация. Инновационная деятельность характерна для современных условий одного уровня или любого производственного предприятия. Даже если компания не является лидером инновационного рынка, рано или поздно она столкнется с необходимостью замены морально устаревших технологий и продуктов. В данной статье анализируются такие вопросы, как психологическая оценка психического состояния сотрудников и определение путей их устранения средствами психологии управления, а также дается информация о целях и задачах психологии управления.

Ключевые слова: инновации, менеджмент, психология, работник, работодатель, менеджмент, предприятие, система, бренд, бизнес, менеджмент, интерфейс, рынок, операционный, маркетинг.

Psychology is the science of mind and behavior. Psychology includes the study of conscious and unconscious phenomena, as well as feelings and thoughts. This field is a very large scientific discipline. Psychologists join the neuroscientific group of researchers who seek to understand emergent properties of the brain and the various phenomena associated with these emergent properties. As a social science, it aims to understand individuals and groups by establishing general principles and studying specific cases [1]

Innovation management is a vague concept related to the field of management, the objects of which are innovation and the innovation process.

Innovation management is a method (technology) of a new or improved product (goods, work, service), its production or application, innovation or organization of production and (or) improvement of the economy and (or) product sales, which brings economic benefits. creating conditions for benefits or improving consumer characteristics of products (goods, works, services).

Innovation process is the process of creation, acquisition, distribution and use of innovation. Also, the innovation process in relation to a product (goods) can be defined as the

process of consistently turning an idea into a product through the stages of fundamental and applied research, design development, marketing, production and sales.

The purpose of management psychology and its practical application is primarily to solve the following problems existing in the organization:

- increase the professional powers of managers;
- improvement of management methods, communication skills, decision-making, strategic planning skills, overcoming stress;
- analysis and improvement of methods of training the management personnel of the company;
- search and activation of personnel resources;
- assessment and selection of managers according to the needs of the company;
- assessment and improvement of the social and psychological climate, increasing the level of loyalty of employees, team building.

Scientific management education appeared in the 80-90s of the 20th century. Its founder was the American engineer F. Taylor, who showed the need for a scientific approach to management in his book "The Method and Principles of Scientific Externalization of Management". The essence of F.Taylor's theory is based on the following principles: □ Scientific approach to the performance of each part of the work.

- A scientific approach to choosing a job, teaching, learning and gaining experience.
- Organization of a team of workers.
- Distribution of responsibility for results between managers and workers.

According to Taylor, there is a best or most convenient way of doing any work, the use of which allows the work to be done with quality and less effort. Taylor chronometers the work done by the workers operating in the enterprise and analyzes it in depth to create a set of rules that ensure efficient work. Taylor's greatest contribution to the development of scientific management was the new management system he proposed. He divides labor into two types: the first - executors, the second - managers.

According to Taylor, every employee should fulfill his duty. In particular, the duties of an administrative manager include drawing up work plans, choosing the most convenient method of execution for each job or operation, recruiting workers on the basis of selection, training, etc.

Another important aspect of Taylor's theory is that it aims to ensure the harmony of relations between administrative management and workers. G. Emerson is one of the scientists who made a significant contribution to the scientific organization of management work. He developed a systematic approach to the organization of management work. His book "12 Principles of Productivity" reveals the essence of a systematic approach. The principles proposed by G. Emerson are as follows:

1. Clarity of purpose;
2. Consistency of logic;
3. Useful advice;
4. Discipline;
5. Human relations;
6. Fast, reliable, complete, accurate and permanent settlement;

7. Dispatching activities;
8. Availability of normative indicators and tables;
9. Availability of working conditions;
10. Marks of exact time for performing types of work or performing operations;
11. Availability of written standard instructions;
12. Promotion of productive cocktails.

The object of management is the personnel of enterprises, organizations and institutions. As an object, not individual employees, but only the labor team should be considered, because only the team is subject to a set of laws and rules that are directed to the production of the finished product and determine the behavior of the system as a whole.

Each leader or boss is unique and irreplaceable. The reason for this is that each boss organizes his work in his own way. One of the problems studied in detail in social psychology is different management styles. In this field, German scientists G. Gibbs and M. Forverg, Russian scientists V. D. Parigin, L. N. Umansky, M. Yu. Zhukov, etc. works are particularly noteworthy.

Thus, the main task of management psychology is to form leadership methods based on the patterns identified in the process of learning between the tactics of the boss and the reaction of subordinates. Usually, the tasks of management psychology can be divided into several large groups depending on the object of research:

- Psychological analysis of management activities. The leader must consciously perform management activities by analyzing the actions necessary to make the right management decisions.
- Learning the mechanisms of mental regulation. It is very important to make the right decision in normal and extreme conditions.
- Leadership studies. Development of leadership qualities necessary for the manager to manage the work process.
- Practical application of psychological knowledge in management processes. This task includes resolving conflicts, regulating the microclimate, increasing job satisfaction and achieving a high level of employee loyalty.
- Studying the interaction of groups. It is necessary to achieve a stable social microclimate in the team.
- To study methods and mechanisms of motivation. Motivation is important in management processes to encourage employees to achieve more meaningful goals.

Management psychology is an interdisciplinary discipline that successfully uses management methods together with psychological methods. The structure of management psychology distinguishes two main research methods: observation and experiment.

Observation is an analytical method based on cognitive processes. This method is the most difficult objective method, because observation is carried out in natural conditions, and the role and position of the observer, respectively, affects and affects the object of observation. Studying and searching for effective principles of interaction between the leader and the team is carried out passively.

During the study, reactions, opinions and results are recorded. This method is used both in obtaining preliminary materials before starting other studies, and in conditions where other methods of obtaining information are not available. Passiveness is the main disadvantage of this

technique. Waiting a long time for the reaction of the object of observation is not always justified, because there is a big risk of missing the moment of reaction and misinterpreting the result. On the other hand, experimentation implies active methods. The search for effective schemes of interaction with the help of experiments is carried out by creating certain conditions for the use of various management tactics.

The purpose of the experiment is to test hypotheses that influence the practice of managerial decision-making.

If the necessary conditions for a successful experiment are met, it is possible to obtain very extensive information of a unique nature with the help of experimental techniques:

- correct selection of control features;
- use of factor properties (introduced by the researcher) to change them;
- to protect the experiment from the maximum external influences unrelated to the situation.

The use of these methods makes it possible to comprehensively study management processes and move on to solving the above problems of management psychology.

In conclusion, it should be noted that management activities are based on certain rules. Adherence to them can lead the company to success, and neglecting them - even under favorable conditions, will lead to its collapse.

Management psychology, its object and subject, allows specialists to develop such rules and methods of behavior, which become not only a form of management, but also a factor. This advances the main task of management psychology as an applied interdisciplinary discipline. In more detail, the subject of management psychology and its object, the practical application of science in management processes, the psychology of the subject of management and the management-oriented object, were considered in other sources on the subject of personnel management and caused a lot of controversy. Management activities are very important in organizing the work of any enterprise or organization. The study of the main principles and guidelines of this direction led to recognition as a special branch of applied psychology, which received this name. It is based on a comprehensive analysis of existing conditions and determination of activity characteristics to achieve high efficiency of labor or social team work.

Management psychology, like any type of scientific work, defines the subject, object, task and methods that allow to create a logical structure. When considering this issue, first of all, we mean the problems of a person (leader) as a member of a team in the implementation of management activities. It should be noted that the effectiveness of the management system in this case depends on the personal characteristics of the leader, which determines his ability to perform diagnostics and also motivates the latter to successfully achieve goals. Thus, the subject of management psychology can be called a complex of psychological relations between a boss and a subordinate or a team, which includes the mechanism of interaction, problems and conflicts of work, social and professional relations.

The object of management psychology should be understood, first of all, as an object of study, that is, the activity of a person (leader) aimed at forming material and social factors in the team. In some cases, this role may be triggered by a specific situation or circumstances that need to be reviewed and analyzed to identify errors or, conversely, positive factors.

The objects of study of management psychology can be divided into three separate groups:
- The leader's personality, as well as his development process as a result of management activities;

- Manager's activity, the scheme of its implementation, and the works from the point of view of efficiency;

- Processes occurring in the social or labor community.

Objectives, principles and methods of management Objectives and main tasks can be defined for any type of activity. If we talk about management psychology, it is clear that the priority instructions are to increase efficiency and can be achieved using certain methods and schemes.

Based on this, the main task of management psychology is the formation of different methods of leadership based on the determined patterns between the tactics of the boss and the reaction of subordinates.

A distinctive feature of management psychology is that its object is the organized activity of people, that is, it is not only the joint activity of people united by common interests or goals, sympathy or values, but also the activity of people who are united in one organization and subordinate to one thing. perform the rules and regulations of this organization and the work added to them in accordance with economic, technological, legal, organizational and corporate requirements). These rules, standards, and requirements of the organization create special psychological relationships among people that exist only in the organization - management relationships.

In management psychology, both the individual worker and the social group and community act in the context of the organization to which they belong. Without organization, their management analysis is incomplete. Summarizing all that has been said, we can conclude that the subject of management psychology is a set of mental phenomena and relationships in the organization:

- Psychological factors of managers' effective activity;
- Psychological characteristics of individual and group decision-making;
- Psychological problems of leadership;
- Management relations consist of problems of motivating the behavior of the subjects and others.

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